

Exchange and Non-Exchange Behaviour of Cationic Species in the Interaction of Metal Ions with Humic and Fulvic Acids*

M. V. M. DESAI

Health Physics Division, Bhabha Atomic Research Centre, Bombay

and

A. K. GANGULY

National Fellow in Environmental Sciences,
Department of Science and Technology, N. Delhi.

Humic substances are high molecular weight organopolymetallic polymeric complexes containing functional groups such as -NH_2 , -COOH and -OH . They contain many trace elements such as Fe, Al, Cu, Zn, Mn etc. in their structure and are capable of solubilising by complexation, a number of elements. In their interaction with added ions, alkali and alkaline earth elements are held at exchangeable cationic sites; transition and trivalent elements are held at cationic and non-cationic sites or as non-exchangeable metal complexes, whereas heavy elements are mostly complexed at non-cationic or non-exchangeable states.

Prof. Mukherjee's early interest in the ion-exchange properties of silicate minerals related to soils and clays extended in later years to the exchange properties of soil humus. Besides the presence of exchangeable ions on the clay mineral surface there always exist in plenty, large variety of non-exchangeable ionic species in the inaccessible crystal matrix. Recent experimental evidences show that humus materials although, basically, are amorphous organic compounds, bear some qualitative similarity with clay minerals, in respect of the presence of exchangeable and non-exchangeable ionic species in their matrix. The present work deals with this aspect of humus materials properties—specifically of humic and fulvic acids.

Humic matter in soils, aquatic sediments, terrestrial waters and sea waters are composed of polyionic complexes containing aliphatic chains and aromatic nuclei, with functional groups such as -NH_2 , -OH and -COOH ¹. These are condensation products of a large variety of organic monomers and polymers, produced by the natural chemical and biochemical degradation of biopolymers and other organic compounds in the biosphere. These products we looked upon as 'random-polymers', wherein the monomeric composition and sequence are determined by the physico-chemical environment in which these are formed². As such, these are illdefined organic high molecular weight compounds having a

number of general physico-chemical characteristics, such as: UV-visible absorption and fluorescence spectra, elemental composition, base exchange characteristics, functional groups etc.

Humic substance is easily separable into three fractions: Humic acid—which is alkali soluble and acid insoluble; Fulvic acid—which is soluble in acid and in alkali; and Humin—which is insoluble in acid and alkali.

Preparation

Humic acid (HA) and Fulvic acid (FA) extracted from a sample of black-cotton soil and samples of coastal marine sediments were studied. Black cotton soil was collected from Amravati (Maharashtra), coastal marine sediments were collected from Bombay Harbour estuarine bay (Trombay naval jetty), shelf sediment I (SSI) from 34 kms off shore (at 50 m depth) and shelf sediment II (SS II) from 113 kms off shore (at 90 m depth) west of Bombay.

The samples were slurried, strained through 100 mesh screen, digested with 0.2 N NaOH + 0.2 N Na_2CO_3 mixture (solid sample: water and alkali mixture 1:10 wt/wt) for 6 hours at 80° under continuous stirring condition and allowed to stand overnight. The supernatant was collected by siphoning and the residue was treated the same way several times for

* The paper is presented in humble homage to a teacher and mentor in Prof. S. K. Mukherjee, on the occasion of his 65th birth anniversary. Prof. Mukherjee pioneered research on Ion-exchange phenomenon in the country and one of us (A. K.G.) was a privileged one to be initiated by him into this field of research, as early as in 1939. The field still continues to be lively and productive both in theory and in applications.

completion of extraction. Supernatants were pooled together, centrifuged at 5500 rpm and the residue rejected.

A portion of the centrifuged extract was purified by simple dialysis till the dialyzate was free of free alkali. It was filtered through 0.22 μ m membrane filter and designated as the mildly purified HAFA.

The rest of the extract was acidified with hydrochloric acid to pH 2 to precipitate HA and allowed to stand overnight. The straw yellow/orange coloured supernatant (FA) was siphoned and collected. The HA coagulate was centrifuged and the supernatant was mixed with the supernatant FA solution.

Purification

Humic acid: HA was treated with ammonia under slightly warm condition, allowed to stand overnight, centrifuged and the residue rejected. The reject was found to contain profuse quantities of Al and Fe. HA was precipitated from the supernatant, centrifuged and the supernatant discarded. The process was repeated till no residue was obtained on centrifugation of ammoniacal supernatant. The ammoniacal solution of HA was filtered through 0.22 μ m membrane filter. A small residue was observed to be retained on the filter. Since this residue, although disperses easily in ammonia, did not pass through the membrane filter, it was rejected. The fraction that passed through the 0.22 μ m membrane filter was than purified by dialysis and prolonged electro dialysis³ as described below :

Fulvic acid: FA fraction was treated with ammonia when a bulky white-brown precipitate dominantly of Al(OH)₃ appeared. This was removed by filtration through Whatman filter No.1, pH of the filtrate was brought back to 2 with hydrochloric acid, centrifuged and the supernatant made ammoniacal again, allowed to stand overnight and filtered through membrane filter. This procedure was repeated several times till no precipitate appeared on addition of ammonia. The FA solution was then concentrated by evaporation under an infra red lamp at a temperature not exceeding 60°, filtered through 0.22 μ m membrane filter, filtrate brought back to pH 2 and purified by dialysis and electro dialysis³.

Purification by Dialysis and Electro dialysis :

HA and FA solutions were charged into the central compartment of an electro dialysis cell and the platinum electrode compartments were filled with doubly distilled water (DDW). Water in the electrode compartments was changed intermittently and the sample in the central compartment stirred often. Dialysis was continued till the electrode compartment water did not give a positive test for chloride.

The solutions were then electro dialysed. The initial DC voltage applied was 5V which was progressively increased in steps upto 200V and the water in the electrode compartments was replaced with DDW at frequent intervals. Conductance of the cathode compartment water was followed and electro dialysis was continued till the conductance of the water in the cathode compartment remained the same as that of DDW (used for filling the compartments) during 24 hours of electro dialysis at 200V. For collecting the dialysed product polarity of the electrodes was changed intermittently to dislodge the purified HA and FA adhering to the membrane.

It was observed, during electro dialysis at 200V, that the conductance of anode compartment water went up abruptly at the termination time of dialysis. Colouring matter appeared in the anode compartment, indicating breakdown of HA and FA polymeric molecules. Anode compartment water on such occasions was tested for phosphate, carbohydrates and amino acids and their presence confirmed the breakdown of HA and FA. The acids thus prepared and purified were stored in well cleaned, steamed glass reagent bottles. The sample thus obtained is designated as drastically purified HA and FA.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric Titration of Humic acids.

TABLE-1. BASE EXCHANGE CAPACITY OF HUMIC AND FULVIC ACIDS

Humic or Fulvic acid	Exchange capacity meq/100 gms
Black cotton soil humic acid	723
Coastal marine humic acid	383
*Shelf Sediment I (SS I) humic acid	293
**Shelf sediment II (SS II) humic acid	225
Black cotton soil fulvic acid	447
Shelf sediment I (SS I) fulvic acid	147

*34 km off-shore at 50 m depth

**113 km off shore at 90 m depth

Potentiometric titration :

Potentiometric titration of drastically purified HA and FA was carried out with standard KOH solution by the use of a pH meter. The titration was carried out also with the sample in half saturated KCl medium. The titration curves are given in

Fig. 2. Potentiometric Titration of Fulvic acids.

figures 1, 2 and 3. The base exchange capacity values obtained are given in Table 1^{2,3}.

Ash and Trace elements in mildly purified HAFA :

An aliquot of the mildly purified HAFA taken in ammonia (2N) was passed through a Dowex-50 W×8 (10 cm×1 cm) NH₄⁺ column (equilibrated with 2N ammonia), first at the rate of 1 ml/min and a part of the effluent was again passed through

Fig. 3. Potentiometric Titration of Humic acids II.

another similar column at the rate of 0.1 ml/min. The amount of ion exchange resin used was overwhelmingly in excess to that required to exchange

all the metal ions being loaded on the column. The HAFA and the two effluents were wet ashed and analysed for trace elements. The results are given in Tables 2 and 3.

Drastically purified HA and FA :

The drastically purified HA and FA were wet ashed and analysed for trace elements. Results obtained are given in Tables 4, 5 and 6.

TABLE-2. TRACE ELEMENTS IN MILDLY PURIFIED HUMUS FROM COASTAL MARINE SEDIMENT

Element	Before passing through Dowex-50	Concentration (ppm)	
		After first pass at 1 ml/min	After second pass at 0.1ml/min
P as PO ₄	10240	10240	10240
Al	1480	1480	1480
Fe	1395	1245	1245
Cu	2430	2305	2070
Mn	250	250	130
Co	130	120	60
Zn	750	300	210
Mg	1725	1725	615
Ca	8035	1125	340

Relative stability order :

TABLE-3. METAL IONS IN COASTAL MARINE HUMUS

	Metal ions meq/100 gms	Exchangeable meq/100 gms
Mildly purified HAFA	89.5	51.8
First pass through Dowex-50 at 1 ml/min	52.5	-
Second pass through Dowex-50 at 0.1 ml/min	37.7	-
Electrodialysed coastal marine HA	44.4	-
Total base exchange capacity of coastal marine HA	-	383

TABLE-4. ASH AND TRACE ELEMENTS IN ELECTRODIALYSED HUMIC ACIDS

Element	Concentration			
	Coastal	SS I	SS II	BC soil
Ash (%)	1.0	2.9	3.0	7.0
SiO ₂	Nil	Nil	Nil	Nil
SO ₄	ND	ND	ND	ND
PO ₄ (ppm)	3225	3675	1250	2540
Al	3480	9865	2850	2975
Fe	180	1655	5920	7470
Cu	1380	1430	815	1275
Zn	-	2520	1060	685
Mg	20	205	340	295
Mn	ND	25	410	140
Ca	ND	ND	ND	ND
Sr	ND	ND	ND	ND
Cr	85	15	-	-
K	80	130	ND	720

Behaviour of HA and FA on Ion-exchange column :

When passed through strongly acidic cation exchange resin in NH₄⁺ form, both HA and FA, in

ammoniacal solutions, were found to escape through the column without being adsorbed. On passing through a strongly basic anion exchanger, these were almost quantitatively retained on the column. Efforts for desorption of the HA and FA from the anion column were unsuccessful, indicating very strong

Solubilisation of trace elements by HA and FA in ammoniacal (for Cu it is dil. NaOH medium) medium (pH~10) was studied using $^{133}\text{Ba}^{2+}$, $^{65}\text{Zn}^{2+}$, $^{54}\text{Mn}^{2+}$, $^{60}\text{Co}^{2+}$, $^{59}\text{Fe}^{3+}$, $^{144}\text{Ce}^{4+}$ as chloride, $^{110m}\text{Ag}^{1+}$, $^{234}\text{Th}^{4+}$ as nitrate of known specific activity and Cu^{2+} as sulphate solutions. The HA and FA solutions with known quantities of salt solutions were kept for a week with intermittent shaking, filtered through 0.22 μm membrane and aliquots of the respective filtrates were analysed

TABLE—5. ASH AND TRACE ELEMENTS IN ELECTRODIALYSED FULVIC ACIDS

Element	Concentration		
	SS I	SS II	BC soil
Ash (%)	2.6	-	9.6
SiO_2	Nil	Nil	Nil
SO_4	ND	ND	ND
PO_4 (ppm)	10720	7755	8525
Al	2455	13730	2770
Fe	ND	22390	2825
Cu	225	ND	795
Zn	=	ND	790
Mg	430	1395	440
Mn	180	780	ND
Ca	515	ND	200
Sr	ND	ND	ND
Cr	ND	-	285
K	355	700	215

TABLE—6. METAL IONS IN ELECTRODIALYSED HUMIC AND FULVIC ACIDS

Humic or fulvic acid	Ash content %	Metal ions meq/100 gms	Base exchange capacity meq/100 gms
<i>Humic acids :</i>			
Coastal marine	1.0	44.4	383
SS I	2.9	133.7	293
SS II	3.0	73.6	225
Black cotton soil	7.0	84.0	725
<i>Fulvic acids :</i>			
SS I	2.6	35.7	147
SS II	22.1	289.0	-
Black cotton soil	9.7	56.0	447

binding of the ligands in HA and FA on the column. The phosphate content in HA and FA were found earlier to be non-exchangeable with any of competing anion in solution. It is thus felt to be covalently bound to the HA and FA polymer matrix.

Interaction properties :

Interaction properties were studied by ion exchange method in alkaline and sea water media. The metal ions solubilised* by HA and FA are characterised in the present work, as of non-cationic and or non-exchangeable forms when the solubilised metal ions pass unadsorbed (or unexchanged) along with HA and FA through a strongly acidic cation exchanger.

* Solubilisation : Metal ions or compounds, normally precipitating or insoluble in the medium, retained in solution or dissolved by ammonium (or sodium) humates and fulvates accompanying them when passed through 0.22 μm membrane filter.

TABLE—7. SOLUBILISATION OF SOME METAL IONS BY MARINE HUMIC AND FULVIC ACIDS

Element	Solubilisation mg/g	
	Humic acid	Fulvic acid (SS I)
Ba^{2+}	263	-
Ag^{+1}	7.50	-
Zn^{2+}	5.97	41.51
Mn^{2+}	8	85.70
Co^{2+}	33.80	22.80
Cu^{2+}	3.70	-
Fe^{3+}	15.40	34.22
Ce^{+3}	4.80	-
Th^{+4}	2.85	8.72

TABLE—8. NATURE OF METAL ION COMPLEXES OF MARINE HUMIC AND FULVIC ACIDS

Element	% non-cationic of the solubilized	
	Humic acid (coastal)	Fulvic acid (SS I)
Ba^{2+}	0	-
Zn^{2+}	12.4	0
Mn^{2+}	42	66
Co^{2+}	64	35
Cu^{2+}	100	-
Fe^{3+}	100	90
Ce^{+3}	90	-
Th^{+4}	100	100

TABLE—9. SOLUBILIZATION AND COMPLEXATION OF METAL IONS BY COASTAL HUMIC ACID

Element	Solubilization meq/100 gms	non-exchangeable Exchangeable	
		complexation	complexation
Ba^{2+}	383	0	383
Ag^{+1}	6.95	0.56	6.39
Zn^{2+}	18.26	2.26	16.00
Mn^{2+}	29.12	12.23	16.89
Co^{2+}	114.70	73.40	41.30
Cu^{2+}	11.60	11.60	0
Fe^{3+}	82.70	82.70	0
Ce^{+3}	10.30	9.20	1.10
Th^{+4}	4.90	4.90	0

TABLE—10. SOLUBILIZATION AND COMPLEXATION OF METAL IONS BY MARINE FULVIC ACID (SS I)

Element	Solubilization meq/100 gms	non-exchangeable Exchangeable	
		complexation	complexation
Zn^{2+}	127	0	127
Mn^{2+}	312	206	106
Co^{2+}	77.4	27.1	50.3
Fe^{3+}	184	165	19
Th^{+4}	15	15	0

for the added trace elements. Another aliquot of each of the filtrates was passed through Dowex-50 ($\times 8\text{NA}_4^+$ form) column at the flow rate of 0.2 ml/min, and the effluent and washings were also analysed for the trace elements. Results are given in Tables 7,8,9 and 10.

Fig. 4. Interaction of $\text{Sr}^{90} - \text{Y}^{90}$ with Humic acid.

Differential interaction studies :

Similar interaction studies were conducted with marine HA and FA using radioactive parent-daughter pairs $^{90}\text{Sr} - ^{90}\text{Y}$, $^{140}\text{Ba} - ^{140}\text{La}$ and $^{228}\text{Ra} - ^{228}\text{Ac}$. Results are given in figures 4,5 and 6.

Fig. 5. Interaction of $\text{Ba}^{140} - \text{La}^{140}$ with Humic acid.

Discussion

Potentiometric titration : Potentiometric titration curves of marine and soil HA and FA show two inflections due to two weak acid groups corres-

ponding to $-\text{COOH}$ and $-\text{OH}$ groups (cf. figures 1 and 2). In half saturated KCl medium also, two inflection points were observed (cf. figure 3). It is to be noted

Fig. 6. Interaction of $\text{Ra}^{228} - \text{Ac}^{228}$ with Humic acid.

that the initial pH in half saturated KCl is down from 3.3 to 3.1 due to the release of H^+ by K^+ ions. The titration curve for black cotton soil FA gave only one inflection. It is observed that the exchange capacity values of the HA reduced as the distance from the shore increases (cf. table 1).

Ash and trace elements :

Mildly purified HAFA : The data in table 2 indicate the ion exchange characteristics of the elements associated with the HAFA. The relative stability order of the metal ions binding with the humus material is $\text{Al}^{3+} > \text{Fe}^{3+} > \text{Cu}^{1+} > \text{Mn}^{2+} > \text{Co}^{2+} \gg \text{Mg}^{2+} > \text{Zn}^{2+} > \text{Ca}^{2+}$ (cf. table 2). Although only bi- and trivalent elements are indicated here, monovalent metal ions are quantitatively exchangeable as is shown by base exchange capacity measurements of HA with Na^+ or K^+ . Table 3 indicates that although the base exchange capacity of HA is 383 meq/100 gms, metal ion analysis of the dialysed material accounts for about 90 meq/100 gms. It is understood that the remaining 290 meq are taken up by NH_4^+ ions since the experiments were performed in ammoniacal medium. On a first pass through a synthetic cation exchanger, 38 meq of metal ions consisting mostly of bivalent metal ions are exchanged. Dominantly exchanging metal ions are Ca^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Co^{2+} , Mn^{2+} and Cu^{1+} . Al^{3+} and Fe^{3+} do not exchange at all. The binding of these metal ions is stronger than the rest or a good part of these are at non-exchangeable positions, 38 meq remaining non-exchanged after the second

pass. The trace elements' content of the electro-dialysed HA sample amount to 44 meq/100 gms which is close to the value of the twice column passed HAFA material.

Drastically purified HA and FA :

Tables 4 and 5 give the trace elements' content of electro-dialysed HA and FA.

Electrodialysis even to the point of breakdown of HA and FA molecules did not result in ash free samples. So it appears that these inaccessible trace elements are integral parts of the structure of HA and FA (cf. also previous section).

The sum of all the analysed trace elements does not agree with the ash content. These trace elements are more or less composed of the non-exchangeable species. It is interesting to see that Ca^{+2} and Sr^{+2} are not detected in the ash of HA i.e., exchangeable Ca^{+2} and Sr^{+2} were removed by electro-dialysis. However, all Ca^{+2} could not be removed from FA during electro-dialysis (cf. table 5): Potassium content in HA and FA is significant. Though this is a monovalent cation, it has not been removed during electro-dialysis. This suggests that it remains inaccessible in the matrix as a structural part of the HA and FA along with Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , Cu^{2+} etc.

Earlier workers viewed the structures of HA and FA as only polymeric organic compounds. However, it is now particularly important to take cognizance of the metallic ions present in the HA and FA structures as participants in the build-up of the polymeric humus complex—either covalently bound or present as shielded ionic complexes.

Table 6 shows that the base exchange capacity is always higher compared to the metal ions in the ash. These metal ions are not parts in the exchangeable species of cations present in the polymeric materials.

Interaction properties :

Data in tables 7 and 8 indicate the extent of solubilisation of added metal ions by marine HA (coastal) and FA (SSI). Significant amounts of each metal ion are solubilised by HA and FA although these normally precipitate out under the alkaline condition in which the experiments were performed. It is seen that alkaline earth ions such as Ba^{2+} are solubilised in amount equivalent to the exchange capacity of the HA and it is quantitatively exchanged on a cation column. The other bi- and trivalent and heavy metal ions listed in the table are held at non-cationic sites, significantly to the extent of 40-100%. Tables 9 and 10 indicate the equivalents of the metal ions solubilised in complexed (in non-cationic forms) and exchangeable forms. In case of the HA (coastal marine) whose exchange capacity is 383 meq/100 gms, no added metal ion except for the alkaline earth

ions is solubilised to the extent equivalent to its exchange capacity (cf. table 9). In many cases very little of the solubilised ions is exchangeable. Similar observation also applies to FA. However, Mn and Fe are observed to be solubilised by FA (exchange capacity 147 meq/100 gms) in excess of its exchange capacity. But of this, exchangeable fraction is less than the exchange capacity (cf. table 10). Earlier observation that the trace element content of the humic materials need not always be in exchangeable forms is further supported by these observations.

Differential interaction studies :

Studies of the interactions with radioactive pairs ^{90}Sr - ^{90}Y , ^{140}Ba - ^{140}La and ^{228}Ra - ^{228}Ac of HA and FA are illustrated in figures 4, 5 and 6. Alkaline earth and rare earth and actinide ions are solubilised by HA and FA. On passage through a cation column, all alkaline earth metal ions are exchanged while rare earth and/or actinide metal ions escape from the column with HA and FA. The decay of radioactivity in the column effluent is shown in the figures 4, 5 and 6. Radioactivity in the effluents

TABLE--11. INTERACTION OF HUMIC ACID WITH TRACE ELEMENTS IN ALKALI AND SEA WATER MEDIA

Element	% non-cationic in	
	Alkali	Sea water
Cs	-	0
K	-	0
Ba	0	0
Sr	0	0
Ra	0	0
Zn	12.4	20.3
Mn	42	100
Co	64	91
La	100	100
Y	100	100
Ac	100	100

decays with the characteristic half-lives of the daughter nuclides ^{90}Y (64 hrs), ^{140}La (40 hrs,) and ^{228}Ac (6 hrs). The parent alkaline earth metal ions on the column upon elution built up to saturation activity as expected are also shown in the figures 4, 5 and 6. Similar behaviour was seen also in sea water medium. Table 11 gives the extent of non-cationic association of solubilised/dissolved ions— Ba^{+2} , Sr^{+2} , Ra^{+2} , Zn^{+2} , Mn^{+2} , Co^{+2} , La^{+3} , Y^{+3} and Ac^{+3} with HA in alkaline and sea water media.

Acknowledgement

We are thankful to BARC authorities for use of their Laboratory facilities for this work.

References

1. W. STUMM and J. J. MORGAN, Aquatic Chemistry, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1970.
2. M. V. M. DESAI and A. K. GANGULY, International Monograph on the Geology and Geochemistry of Manganese, IAGOD Commission, 1979.
3. M. V. M. DESAI and A. K. GANGULY, BARC-488, 1970.